

the reaction (Table 5). The catalytic activity of these ligands under identical conditions follows the order : hydroxyproline > glycine > aspartic acid > alanine. It appears that each amino acid has its own dependence of rate, which is a function of $[L]/[Cr^{VI}]$ and of $[H^+]$. (ii) The rate is proportional to $[ligands]$ at all the $[H^+]$, at which the reaction was studied (Table 4). The catalytic activity of these ligands under identical conditions follows the order : 8-hydroxyquinoline > picolinic acid > salicylic acid > salicylamide > α, α' -dipyridyl > 5-sulphosalicylic acid.

Table 1. Oxidation of lactic acid by Cr^{VI} in presence of picolinic acid (typical run)

$[HClO_4] = 5.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[picolinic \text{ acid}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[lactic \text{ acid}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Cr^{VI}] = 4.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 299 K

Time	Volume of hypo used (a-x) ml	$10^{-4} k_{obs}$ s^{-1}
1.0	20.6	-
10	19.0	1.31
20	17.6	1.31
30	16.2	1.33
40	15.1	1.29
50	13.8	1.33
60	12.9	1.30

Table 2. Variation of rate with concentration of lactic acid in presence of picolinic acid

$[HClO_4] = 5.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[picolinic \text{ acid}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[lactic \text{ acid}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Cr^{VI}] = 4.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 304 K

$10^2 [Lactic \text{ acid}]$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^3 k_{obs}$ s^{-1}	$k_{obs}/[Lactic \text{ acid}]$
1.0	4.24	0.42
1.5	6.42	0.42
2.0	8.05	0.40
3.0	12.20	0.40
4.0	16.20	0.40
5.0	20.05	0.40
6.0	23.40	0.39

Table 3. Variation of rate with concentration of perchloric acid in presence of ligand 4-sulphosalicylic acid

$[Lactic \text{ acid}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Cr^{VI}] = 4.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 304 K

$10^1 [HClO_4]$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^4 k_{obs} s^{-1}$ (Uncatalyzed)	$10^4 k_{obs} s^{-1}$ (Catalyzed)
2.0	0.45	0.55
3.0	0.68	0.83
4.0	0.88	1.16
5.0	1.03	1.38
7.0	1.13	1.93
10.0	1.93	2.80

Table 4. Variation of rate (Δk_{obs}) with $[Ligand]/[Cr^{VI}]$

$[HClO_4] = 5.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[lactic \text{ acid}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Cr^{VI}] = 4.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 299 K

	$[Ligand]/[Cr^{VI}]$	$10^5 \Delta k_{obs}$ s^{-1}	$10^2 \Delta k_{obs}/$ $[Ligand]$
α, α' -Dipyridyl	0.62	5.17	2.23
	1.87	16.6	2.22
	3.12	27.3	2.19
	4.37	36.9	2.21
	5.62	48.7	2.17
8-Hydroxyquinoline	0.37	5.00	3.38
	0.50	6.90	3.45
	0.62	8.00	3.22
	0.75	9.69	3.29
	1.12	15.68	3.50
Picolinic acid	0.61	2.25	0.92
	1.25	4.58	0.93
	1.87	7.42	0.99
	2.50	10.05	1.00
	5.00	18.35	0.92
Salicylic acid	0.93	2.05	0.55
	1.25	3.07	0.61
	1.87	4.78	0.63
	2.50	5.85	0.58
	3.75	8.52	0.57
Salicylic amide	4.37	4.20	0.24
	5.00	4.92	0.25
	8.75	7.95	0.23
	9.37	9.35	0.25
	10.0	9.80	0.24
4-Sulphosalicylic acid	125	3.2	0.0064
	250	6.06	0.0060
	375	8.66	0.0058
	500	11.72	0.0059
	625	15.68	0.0062

$\Delta k_{obs} = [k_{obs} (\text{Catalyzed}) - k_{obs} (\text{Uncatalyzed})]$.

In second category, the ligands like α, α' -dipyridyl, 8-hydroxyquinoline, picolinic acid, salicylic acid, salicylamide and 5-sulphosalicylic acid, the catalysis is observed at all acidities in range 0.2 to 1.2 mol dm^{-3} (Table 4). This is because at all acidities used the complex formation may not proceed to the extent of blocking all the sites of coordination. Ligands like amino acids i.e. glycine, alanine, aspartic acid and hydroxyproline cause increase in the reaction rate under certain conditions. In case of glycine and alanine the catalysis is observed provided the ratio of $[L]/[Cr^{VI}] \leq 2.0$. For higher ratio of $[L]/[Cr^{VI}]$ the presence of ligand causes a decreases in the reaction rate with $[H^+]$ ion concentration. Maxima depends on amino acid and $[L]/[Cr^{VI}]$ indicated by negative sign of Δk_{obs} in Table 5.

Table 5. Variation of rate (Δk_{obs}) with $[\text{Ligand}]/[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]$

$[\text{HClO}_4] = 5.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{lactic acid}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}] = 4.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 299 K

	[Ligand]/ [Cr ^{VI}]	10 ⁵ Δk _{obs} s ⁻¹		
		[H ⁺]=0.5 mol dm ⁻³	[H ⁺]=0.7 mol dm ⁻³	[H ⁺]=1.05 mol dm ⁻³
Hydroxyproline	1.88	0.18	3.02	2.16
	4.87	0.62	3.90	2.55
	6.25	0.92	1.80	1.73
	12.50	-2.33	-0.15	-0.15
	18.75	-2.56	-0.51	-0.54
Alanine	0.50	1.58	2.13	0.90
	1.00	-0.48	0.60	0.31
	1.50	-1.90	0.35	0.07
	2.00	-2.93	-0.15	-0.15
	2.50	-3.65	-0.59	-0.33
Aspartic acid	0.62	0.56	3.00	2.22
	1.25	-0.56	2.33	1.05
	6.25	-1.83	0.48	0.45
	8.75	-2.75	-0.46	0.10
	12.50	-3.35	1.52	-0.12
Glycine	0.25	7.92	6.85	5.66
	1.25	3.33	4.00	2.55
	1.75	1.17	2.02	1.20
	2.25	0.00	0.76	-0.47
	2.50	-1.66	-0.16	-1.40

$$\Delta k_{\text{obs}} = [k_{\text{obs}}(\text{Catalysed}) - k_{\text{obs}}(\text{Uncatalysed})]$$

For hydroxyproline and aspartic acid, catalysis is observed if $[\text{L}]/[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]$ is 10.0. For higher ratio there is rate retardation. The behavior of the ligands and the extent of catalysis caused are dependent on H^+ concentration. Following Peng and Rocek⁴, this is due to precursor complex formation. Choosing amino acid as an example, this can be represented as :

The complex with Cr^{VI} is octahedral. Cr^{VI} is known to exist in octahedral form. Naturally with this type of complex formation three bidentate ligand molecules can occupy the six coordination sites. Sundari *et al.*⁵ also suggested a termolecular complex of picolinic acid and Cr^{VI} in oxidation of mandelic acid by Cr^{VI} catalyzed by picolinic acid. The fact that the catalysis is observed for $[\text{L}]/[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}] = 2.0$ in

case of glycine shows that the remaining two coordination sites are occupied by the lactic acid under conditions where catalysis is observed (Scheme 1(A)). For higher ratios of $[\text{L}]$ to $[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]$, lactic acid can only enter into the coordination sphere of $[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]$ by displacing the ligand molecules from the sphere of coordination (Scheme 1(B)). Thus :

Scheme 1(A)

Complex-C

Scheme 1(B)

where, L is the bidentate ligand. The rate laws can be obtained using steady state concept

$$[\text{C}] = \frac{[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}][\text{LA}]}{K_m + [\text{LA}]}$$

where $K_m = (k'_1 + k'_{-1})/k_1$; L is bidentate ligand and LA is lactic acid

$$\therefore \text{Rate} = k[\text{C}] \frac{k[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}][\text{LA}][\text{L}]}{K_m + [\text{LA}]} = k_{\text{obs}}[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]$$

$$\text{where } k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k[\text{LA}][\text{L}]}{K_m + [\text{LA}]}$$

The plot $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{LA}]$ is a straight line passing through origin.

Observed rate constants at different ligand concentrations keeping $[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]$, $[\text{H}^+]$ and $[\text{LA}]$ constant are summarized in Tables 4 and 5. In most of the cases $\Delta k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{Ligand}]$ is practically a constant (within experimental errors, Table 4), which proves rate to be of first order with respect to

Table 6. Variation of rate with temperature in presence of ligand[HClO₄] = 5.0 × 10⁻¹ mol dm⁻³, [lactic acid] = 2.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, [Cr^{VI}] = 4.0 × 10⁻³

Ligand	[Ligand] mol dm ⁻³	Rate (Catalyzed) 10 ⁵ k _{obs} s ⁻¹				ΔE _a [#] kJ mol ⁻¹ (Catalyzed)
		299 K	304 K	309 K	314 K	
α,α'-Dipyridyl	2.0 × 10 ⁻³	3.13	3.28	3.42	3.57	6.66 ± 0.26
8-Hydroxy quinoline	2.0 × 10 ⁻³	5.30	5.60	6.10	6.40	9.99 ± 0.34
Picolinic acid	2.5 × 10 ⁻³	2.01	2.13	2.14	2.40	7.71 ± 0.29
Salicylic acid	3.0 × 10 ⁻³	0.58	0.61	0.63	0.67	6.67 ± 0.26
Salicylamide	2.0 × 10 ⁻²	3.10	3.31	3.40	3.91	12.89 ± 0.53
4-Sulphosalicylic acid	0.5	2.26	2.30	2.45	2.57	6.76 ± 0.27
Hydroxyproline	1.0 × 10 ⁻²	4.88	5.50	5.83	6.16	11.29 ± 0.46
Glycine	1.0 × 10 ⁻²	4.23	4.50	4.75	5.00	8.52 ± 0.32
Aspartic acid	1.0 × 10 ⁻²	3.73	4.00	4.28	4.55	10.20 ± 0.42
Alanine	1.0 × 10 ⁻²	3.00	3.17	3.35	3.52	7.89 ± 0.32

ligand. Although 2 to 3 molecules of ligand are taking part in the reaction with Cr^{VI} but experimentally, the order observed w.r.t. ligand is one. In case of amino acids, behavior is different. Each amino acid has a maxima in rate depending on the nature of amino acid, [H⁺] and [Ligand]/[Cr^{VI}] ratio.

The Cr^{VI}-ligand complex is a better oxidant than Cr^{VI} alone. The Cr^{VI}-ligand complex and lactic acid may react with a precursor complex formation, which decompose in the rate-limiting step as suggested in Scheme 1(A). However, plot of 1/k_{obs} vs 1/[LA] is a straight line passing through origin in all the cases. There is no kinetic evidence of complex formation. These complexes seem to be labile. The free radical produced in the initial step reacts with Cr^{VI} to give aldehyde and Cr^V, which in turn will react with lactic acid to form CH₃CO.COOH by a two-electron step. Thus activation of Cr^{VI} by complex formation leads to increase in reaction rate and the ratio of pyruvic acid to acet-aldehyde is 2 : 1 as observed.

There is no induced polymerization indicating that the radicals rapidly react with Cr^{VI}. The fact that catalysis is observed in case of glycine and alanine for [L]/[Cr^{VI}] ≤ 2.0 indicates that the complex of Cr^{VI} with glycine and alanine has a large formation constant. In case of aspartic acid and hydroxyproline the catalysis observed upto ratio [L]/[Cr^{VI}] = 10.0 indicates that the complex is labile. Thus on the basis of the explanation advanced the ligands cause catalysis or inhibition depending on the conditions of experiments i.e. [L]/[Cr^{VI}] ratio, acidity etc. The order with respect to lactic acid is one and since the smallest ratio of [L]/[Cr^{VI}] under which acceleration effect is observed is ≤ 2.0, it is unlikely that this reaction involves a single step three electron oxidation as proposed by Rocek and Hasan^{10,11}. The fact that two third of product is pyruvic acid indicates that Cr^{VI} changes to Cr^{IV} in the oxidation of lactic acid and Cr^{IV} brings about further oxidation of lactic acid by one electron change. It is

now well known that Cr^{VI} and Cr^V affect C-H bond rupture¹² while Cr^{IV} is responsible for C-C cleavage products¹³ in case of oxidation of α-substituted acids. The temperature effect indicates a very low value of ΔE_a[#] for the catalyzed reaction. This may be due to the overall value of ΔE_a[#] for various substitution equilibrium involved in the system.

Inhibition :

Rate retardation with increase in ligands concentration after optimum [L]/[Cr^{VI}] can be explained with Scheme 1(B). When the coordination sphere of Cr^{VI} is fully occupied, the lactic acid can only enter the sphere of coordination by displacing L as shown in equilibrium. Addition of ligand, H₂L, decreases the rate by decreasing the concentration of complex C.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were either AnalaR grade or were purified, and purity checked by m.p. or b.p. The reactions were carried out in a thermostat (±0.05°). Decrease in the concentration of Cr^{VI} was followed iodometrically taking all the usual precautions. First order rate constants were calculated graphically [plots of log (a-x) vs t] and checked using linear least squares method. k values have standard deviation of ±0.2. The reaction stoichiometry (catalyzed and uncatalyzed) corresponds to the equation :

No free radical formation was detected in polymerization test. Product study was made under kinetic conditions in the presence and absence of the ligands. The oxidized reaction mixture was completely neutralized by sodium bicarbonate and then extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was used for the detection and determination of acetaldehyde while aqueous layer was used to detect and estimate pyruvic acid. In both the cases aqueous HCl solution of

2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine was used to precipitate the hydrazones. The products were qualitatively checked by m.p. and mixed m.p. of the hydrazones of pyruvic acid (m.p. 218°) and that of acetaldehyde (m.p. 168°). Parallel blanks were made in the estimation and the % yield corrected accordingly. The ratio of acetaldehyde to pyruvic acid was always found to be 1 : 2 whether the reaction was catalyzed (by all the ligands) or uncatalyzed.

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References

1. S. Meenakshisundaram and R. Vinothini, *Croatia Chemica Acta*, 2003, **76**, 75.
2. V. Sathiyendran, Ph.D. Thesis, Annamalai University, 1999, 175; P. Uma, P. K. Rao and M. N. Shastri, *React. Kinet. Catal. Lett.*, 1989, **39**, 255.
3. A. Chellamani and V. Rajarajeswari, *Afinidad*, 1999, **56**, 322.
4. T. Y. Peng and H. Rocek, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **98**, 1026.
5. V. Sundari, S. Meenakshisundaram and C. Vasuki, *Oxid. Commun.*, 1999, **22**, 400.
6. G. V. Bakore and C. L. Jain, *Z. Phys. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1970, **1**, 245.
7. G. Mangalam and S. P. Meenakshisundaram, *Pol. J. Chem.*, 1998, **72**, 582.
8. S. P. Meenakshisundaram and R. M. Soekaligam, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 2001, **74**, 1043.
9. Takahiao Nishimura, Tomoaki Onoue, Ohe. Koichi and Shaka Vemara, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1998, **39**, 6071.
10. J. Rocek and F. Hasan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 9073.
11. J. Rocek and F. Hasan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **97**, 1444.
12. J. Rocek and A. E. Radkowsky, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **95**, 7123.
13. K. B. Wiberg and H. Schafer, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 927.